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AUTHORS

Nurullah Kadim
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9594-5979>

Erdal Benli
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8485-1424>

Mevlut Keles
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3508-7495>

Ahmet Yuce
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2931-3927>

Akın Ayaz
<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-4274-5359>

Kaan Mert Yigit
<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-7207-2112>

AFFILIATIONS

Ordu University, Urology Clinic
Ordu, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Hematuria is a prognostic indicator for significant pathologies. Urological cancer may be detected in approximately 20–30% of these patients (Dyrskjøet et al., 2023). When hematuria is accompanied by risk factors for urothelial cancers—such as smoking, irritative voiding symptoms, advanced age, or exposure to chemicals—its prognostic value increases further (DeGeorge et al., 2017). This study was designed to highlight the clinical significance of hematuria detected through a simple urinalysis. Consent for the study was obtained from the patient.

Case Presentation: A 64-year-old male patient, F.B., underwent routine tests at a family medicine clinic. Microscopic hematuria was detected on urinalysis, leading to a referral to our clinic. The patient had no urological complaints upon evaluation. A detailed history and physical examination revealed no pathology except for a history of smoking (44 pack-years). Other than the presence of erythrocytes in the urinalysis (Creatinine: 0.71 mg/dL, PSA: 2.46 ng/mL, urinalysis: 11 erythrocytes), no abnormalities were detected. Urinary ultrasound showed no remarkable findings, and the prostate volume was measured at 44 cc. The patient was informed in detail, and written consent was obtained before recommending urethrocytoscopy. During endoscopy, an approximately 8 mm papillary tumoral lesion was observed on the left posterolateral wall of the bladder. It was resected in the same session, and the specimen was sent for pathological analysis. The patient was discharged without complications on postoperative day 2 after catheter removal. Two weeks later, he returned for follow-up with the pathology report. He remained asymptomatic. Pathological evaluation revealed urothelial carcinoma (noninvasive papillary urothelial carcinoma, pTa low grade). After being informed accordingly, the patient was enrolled in a follow-up program at the uro-oncology outpatient clinic. His follow-up continues uneventfully.

Conclusion: This study demonstrates the significant value of urinalysis, which is a simple and cost-effective diagnostic tool. Hematuria detected in urinalysis must be taken seriously and evaluated from a urological perspective (Bolenz et al., 2018). Most patients with urothelial carcinoma are asymptomatic during the early

stages, which must be kept in mind. All cases of hematuria should be regarded as a potential early sign of cancer until proven otherwise. It is crucial to inform and educate primary care physicians and healthcare providers regarding this issue.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Hematuria, bladder tumor, urinalysis

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Nurullah Kadim

Ordu University, Urology Clinic

Ordu, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9594-5979>

dr.nurullahkadim@gmail.com